

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS AND RESEARCHES ON THE POSSIBLE CAUSES OF THE PRODUCTION ACCIDENT OF THE SIFTING INSTALLATION

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Abstract

Based on materials on the Internet, the features of sifting plants and the technological process of sifting have been studied. The failed coal sifting plant was analyzed and investigated. Welded joints were investigated. The most likely cause of the production accident is the breaking of the suspension of the chute or parts of it due to structural and technological reasons.

Keywords: sifting installation, welded joints, production accident

1. Introduction:

1.1 Peculiarities of sifting installations and the technological process of sifting

The technology for mechanical separation of mixtures of granular materials with different sizes, known as sieving, is widely used in the mining-beneficiation industry and in the processing of inert materials for construction. Depending on their purpose, sifting operations are preparatory, auxiliary, separate or dewatering. In the preparatory processes, the raw material is pre-divided into classes, which subsequently go through various methods of beneficiation. Auxiliary sieving is preliminary and control, and aims to separate the ready-sized class from the general product, so that it does not go through the crushing process unnecessarily. Separating is used for raw materials that are not beneficiation, and after grain-metric preparation, the resulting grades are directly sent to the consumer. The latter type of sieving is applied in the dewatering of big- and fine-grained products obtained by wet enrichment methods. The machines used to sift the materials are called sifting machines. They consist of three main elements: a sieving surface, a frame on which the sieve is mounted and a drive mechanism. Sieves are made of different materials, and the requirement for them is that they do not enter into chemical interaction with the sifted material and have sufficient mechanical resistance. Among the most commonly used are sieves made of metal sheets, in which holes of various sizes and shapes are punched; sieves of braided threads of special steel, non-ferrous metals; sieves composed of bars and roller sieves, representing a system of shafts with interlocking discs that pass the fine material and move the big pieces forward. In addition to the standard types, there are also stretchable sieves made of rubber or highly abrasion-resistant polyurethane, which are used in medium and fine sieving processes.

The location of the sieve holes and their number have a major influence on the sifting efficiency. The placement and movement of the sieves is also important. They can be placed in series, parallel or combined. Sequential placement gives greater comfort in work, but all the material falls on the smallest and

weakest place. In the case of parallel placement, all the material falls on the largest and at the same time strongest sieve, but the individual sieves are more difficult to access. With the combined (modular) placement of the sieves, these disadvantages are removed to some extent.

1.2. Sifting schemes

Sifting is realized in several ways. When the sieving sequence is from big to fine material, the sieving surfaces are mounted one below the other - from largest to smallest hole. This method achieves good sieving efficiency and leads to slower wear of the sieve surfaces, but it requires a large height of the sieving device. The sifting efficiency of the raw material, also called the efficiency of the sifting device, is calculated as the ratio of the mass of the screened product to the mass of material of the same size contained in the feed of the operation. The sifting efficiency in industrial conditions with modern sifting devices is usually in the range of 65 to 90%. In some models, it can be even higher - 98%.

When installing the sieve surfaces from the smallest to the largest hole, sieving from fine to big material is carried out, characterized by lower sieving efficiency and faster wear of the sieves, but also with a smaller height of the sieve installation. Combined sieving avoids some of the disadvantages of the two methods described, but is more complicated to implement and is therefore rarely used.

Sifting can be wet or dry. Depending on the sieve holes, the sieving operations are divided into big sieving (with feed size from 1200 to 0 mm and holes on the sieving surface from 300 to 100 mm); medium sieving (with feed size 350-0 mm and holes on the sieving surface from 60 to 26 mm); petite sieving (with feed size 75-0 mm and holes on the sieving surface from 26 to 6 mm); fine sieving (at feed size 10-0 mm and holes on the sieving surface from 5 to 0.5 mm); very fine sieving (sorting of particles with a sieve hole size of 0.05-0.03 mm). Sifting installations with movement of individual elements on the sifting surface are known as mobile sifting devices. Part of them are roller sifting plants, the sifting surface of which consists of parallel rollers on which round or shaped discs are mounted on a common

frame. The rollers are driven by an engine via a main and intermediate chain drive. The first shaft rotates at the lowest speed, and the last shaft at the end of the unloading of the sifted product - at the highest. Thus, the peripheral speed of the rollers is in the range of 0.8-1.5 m/s. Roller sifting plants are used mainly for sifting coal, coal shale and anthracites and less often for other non-metallic raw materials.

Swinging sifting devices are inclined and horizontal. Horizontal ones carry out differential movement, i.e. the speed of forward movement is less and the speed of backward movement is greater, where the material particles bounce and move. Inclined installations are with inclined and vertical upper suspension, and horizontal ones with inclined upper and lower suspension. A disadvantage of flat-oscillating sifting plants is the occurrence of significant vibrations, which are transmitted to the foundation and the structure of the building. As a type, there are sifting installations with reciprocating movement of the sifting surface. In modern concentrator factories, these installations are being replaced by vibrating screeners. With them, the sifting installation performs rectilinear longitudinal movements created by a crank-fork mechanism. The vibrations have a symmetrical speed diagram and a constant amplitude, independent of the speed mode of operation of the mechanism and the amount of sieved material.

Rotating (drum) sifting machines are also used. Their principle of action is based on the rotary movement of a drum made of individual sieves. The shape of the drum can be cylindrical or multi-walled. Special rotating sifting machines with cylindrical sieves are used to pass and sort materials with different fractions.

1.3. Vibrating sifting plants

Depending on the type of applied vibrations, there are 3 types of vibration plants: with circular, rectilinear and combined vibrations. Depending on the slope of the sifting surface - with a large (15-30°), with a small (5-6°) slope and horizontal. Inclined installations are almost always single, and horizontal ones can also be paired by floor arrangement of the sifting installations. Eccentric, inertial, self-balancing and resonant vibration installations are most widely used. In the case of eccentric sifting installations, the sifting surface receives circular reciprocating movements as a result of the rotation of the crankshaft. The central part of the crankshaft determines the eccentricity, as well as the circular oscillations of the installation. When the center of gravity of the housing coincides with the center of the eccentric, the installation performs circular movements. At both ends of the crate, the oscillations are elliptical because there is uneven material loading. Dynamic balancing of the vibration system is achieved with unbalance weights attached to discs. Eccentric sifting installations are medium and heavy type.

Inertial sifting installations are also widely used. In them, the vibrations are created under the action of an inertial force arising from a rotating inertial mass, and the amplitude of the oscillations is not constant. These installations have a single-shaft vibration mechanism with circular or elliptical oscillations. The drive pulley transmits the movement of the shaft, in which

the discs with the unbalanced weights develop centrifugal inertial forces imparting vibrations to the entire system.

The self-balancing sieving installations are characterized by rectilinear oscillations transmitted by the vibrator to the plane of the sieving surface at an angle of 35-55°, therefore it is not necessary to install the sieve at an angle. The self-balancing vibrator consists of a closed housing in which 2 shafts with fully balanced imbalances rotate in different directions. This type of system is characterized by high efficiency and is used in the washing of suspensions, declamation and dewatering of big and fine coal, sifting of inert materials and hot agglomerate.

Resonant sifting installations are a vibrating system consisting of two parts - a body with a screen and a massive frame connected with flexible elements. They are only of the light type and are used for dewatering large and small coals and some light ores. They have high efficiency and productivity and low energy consumption. The principle of operation is based on the phenomenon of resonance. In order not to destroy the system under the influence of resonance, the frequencies of the forced oscillations created must be greater than the frequencies of the natural oscillations of the system.

Electro vibration sifting installations have a limited application. In them, the vibrations are created by an electric vibrator and transmitted to the body of the device. The oscillations are strictly rectilinear, parallel to the supporting surface of the frame on which the sifting device is mounted.

The main goal of the work is through analyzes and researches to establish the probable cause of the production accident of a sifting plant.

2. Experimental part

A crashed coal sifting plant was analyzed and investigated. Based on materials on the Internet, the features of sifting plants and the technological process of sifting have been studied. The welding joints of the installation were examined. The analyzed installation, with which the materials are sifted, in the case of coal, is a classic sifting installation of the movable vibration type (Fig. 1). It consists of three main elements: a sifting surface, a frame on which the screen is mounted and a drive mechanism. Auxiliary (secondary) elements to the installation are: conveyor belt, drying chamber, chute, "big bag" (sack) in which the sifted coal fraction is collected. The sifting plant implements the so-called independent sifting of raw materials, in this case coal, in which, after grain-metric preparation, the obtained grades are directly sent to the consumer. The technological process of sieving consists of delivery (movement) of the supplied coal fractions of different sizes along the conveyor belt, heating in the drying chamber and vibration sieving of the material. Coal fractions with a suitable grain size composition pass through the sifting surface and are collected in "big bags". The remaining material (coal) moves and falls into the chute and is separated at the sides of the plant. Coal with an inappropriate grain size composition is they also manually fill in "big bags". The technical inspection found changes compared to the technical documentation:

changes (improvements) were made to the chute into which the technological residue from the sifting falls. It was also found that the chute was additionally fabricated and installed, possibly to improve the efficiency of the sifting process. Therefore, the chute is not part of the original sifting installation. Arbitrary introduction of any technical changes is inadmissible without technical supervision. This is a prerequisite for the occurrence of production accidents.

Excavator and forklift have an auxiliary function in the technological process of coal sifting. The forklift pulls the filled "big bag" with the sifted fraction with a suitable particle size composition, then a new, empty

"big bag" is placed. The coal with an inappropriate grain size, which does not pass through the sifting surface (sieve), accumulated on the sides of the installation moves along the chute and is collected in a pile.

It was established that, as a result of the production accident, the chute was not in its original working position, but was significantly displaced. Bearing in mind its dimensions, the material from which it is made and the suspension of the chute, it can be categorically concluded that such a displacement cannot be the result of human impact - the physical effort of a person or a group of people. There are two possible reasons for the suspension of the chute of the sifting plant to be broken:

Fig. 1. General view of the sifting plant

2.1. The chute has undergone a physical-mechanical impact, for example with the bucket of the excavator, by the forklift or other sufficiently powerful technical means or motor vehicle.

2.2. Breakage of the chute suspension in the sifting process when loading or/and overloading with the unsifted particle size fraction due to the following possible reasons: unprofessional specifications for constructing the chute; poorly made chute as construction, material (brand of steel); poor performance (welding) of the chute suspension of the sifting plant. The rupture causes displacement of the chute from its working position, and generally leads to the production accident. On the other hand, the displacement of the chute, regardless of the cause, is a likely factor for traumatic injuries to the service personnel if the same is located under or in the immediate vicinity of the chute of the sifting installation.

Non-destructive investigations were carried out in the Laboratory of non-destructive testing in IMSTCH-BAS. License I-1193 registration number 04328 for using of ionizing ray sources for scientific and economic

purposes. Non-destructive control with radiation methods and with roentgen defectoscope of type 200/5 model MXR-200. Technical parameters: spot focus 2, 45x2, 80 mm; anode current 5 mA; tension 180 kV at measured equivalent dose 0,210 mSv with tapping $\pm 0, 8 \%$. Work conditions and reading of the roentgenograms are conformity with Standards BDS EN ISO [3].

Point of the non-destructive testing: Roentgen (X-ray) or Gamma rays are using in the radiation control methods. They penetrate across optical untransparent bodies and operate over photographer's films similar to light rays. Under their operation some substances like for example Zink sulphide, shining (luminescence).

In the roentgen graphic control the radiation source (Roentgen pipe) is placing at a certain distance from object so as the rays to be direct perpendicularly on the axis. On the contrary side Roentgen film is settings. In the irradiation time (X-ray treatment) the film is situated under action of rays in the course of determinate time named exposition. Follows removal of the film in dark from the cassette, development and fixing in order to obtaining a steady photographer's picture.

As a result on the section of the investigated object on separate places the picture is with irregular degree of tarnish. Rays who fall into film after passing through a defect are absorbing to a smaller degree in comparison with the rays passed through dense metal. First rays cause stronger darkening of determinate section of film.

3. Analysis of the results: possible (probable) causes of the production accident of the sifting plant

After analyzing the features of sifting installations and the technological features of the sifting process in the practice of such workshops, the following most common production accidents are permissible:

3.1. Major damage (explosion) to the sifting plant, including the drying chamber;

3.2. Entry of a foreign body into the sifting installation;

3.3. Physical-mechanical impact (for example, by a motor vehicle such as an excavator, forklift or other) on the chute (the suspension of the chute) and displacement of the same from its working position with subsequent uncoordinated actions of the driver;

3.4. Faulty construction and resulting collapse of the plant. Collapse of the construction of the sieving installation, in the specific case, breakage of the suspension of the chute or parts of it during loading and/or

Fig.2

X-ray photo of a welded plate with defects

This conclusion is also confirmed by the fact that the chute of the coal sifting plant after the production accident was not in the original working position, but was significantly displaced. Taking into account the dimensions, the material from which it is made and the suspension of the chute, it can be concluded that such a displacement cannot be the result of human impact - the physical effort of a person or a group of people. Obviously, there was a break in the suspension of the chute without suffering a physical-mechanical impact. The breakage of the suspension of the chute or parts of it occurred due to design errors and technically poor-quality workmanship of the chute to the sifting installation such as construction, material (brand of steel) and poor-quality suspension of the same (defective welding joints). Depreciation of the installation should also be taken into account.

4. Conclusion

Based on materials on the Internet, the features of sifting plants and the technological process of sifting have been studied. The failed coal sifting plant was analyzed and investigated. Welded joints were investigated. It was found that the chute was not part of the original sifting installation. Arbitrary introduction of any technical changes is a prerequisite for the occurrence of production accidents. It was found that the

overloading in the sieving process with the unsieved particle size fraction. As a result of design errors; poorly made chute such as construction, material (brand of steel) and poor execution (welding) of the chute suspension.

During the inspection of the damaged sifting installation for sifting coal, no damage was found to the installation (except for the chute) for screening coal, including the drying chamber. Hypothetically, it is possible to allow a foreign body (object) to fall into the sifted coal. But the speed of the conveyor belt and the speed at which the coal is screened, as well as the location of the chute, rule out this hypothesis. We have not found any physical-mechanical impact on the chute. As a result of the analysis of sieving installations and the technological process of sieving and the analysis of the welds of the installation, as the most probable cause of the production accident, the rupture of the suspension of the chute or parts of it due to construction and technological reasons is outlined. This is established by the examination and analysis of the welding joints (Fig. 2, 3). The quality of the welding joints was examined by non-destructive testing methods. Defects were found in the welding joints [4,5].

Fig.3

X-ray of a defect-free section

chute of the coal sifting plant after the production accident was not in the original working position, but was significantly displaced (torn). Taking into account the dimensions, the material from which it is made, and the suspension of the same, we can make the definite conclusion that human influence is not able to disrupt the suspension of the chute. Obviously, suspension rupture occurred without physical-mechanical impact. The breakup of the suspension of the chute or parts of it occurred due to design errors; loading and/or overloading with unsieved particle size fraction; technically poor-quality manufacturing of the same in terms of construction, material (brand of steel); poor performance of welding joints. The complex effect of all these factors causes the fatal displacement of the chute from its working position in combination with the impact of a falling mass of coal.

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